

A Study and Analysis of European Funding Projects, Proposals, Steps and Questionnaire Clarifications

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this questionnaire is to provide funding agencies with details information about the project and the real needs of the area it pertains to. It will be used as a basis for the study of your application, so please ensure to answer all the questions in full. This will facilitate the work of both parties. The project proposal composing strategy matters to share as well as define concerning your vision, demand, capacity, ability. Define the problems of the location concerning the project is worried as well as much more especially it represents the account inappropriate as well as the certain manner in which can persuade the funding companies, funding agencies, and the bodies who are the give.

Keywords: Project proposal, European Funding Projects, Questionnaire, Project Ideas, Steps for Funding Projects

1. Introduction

Evaluation of the literature to discover what methods could operate in your scenario. It about the problems and objectives of the community, and deal with companions to establish a treatment for addressing them with the suggested funding. The great technique asks for complete participation of the community and also other partners in all aspects of this work. Create an activity prepare for the intervention. Indicate exactly how you will certainly adjust the intervention or "best practice" to fit the requirements and context of your area (e.g., differences in sources, cultural worths, capability, and language). Recognize the mode of delivery whereby each part as well as an element of the intervention will be provided in the neighborhood (e.g., workshops for skill training). Specify the core elements and elements of the intervention. Recognize and also examine "finest practices" or "evidence-based interventions" that could assist address the issue or goal in your scenario. Establish goals and goals for what "success" would certainly look like. Assess the issue or objectives to be resolved by the intervention. Suggest just how you will certainly get area involvement in determining troubles and also goals to be dealt with by the intervention. Explain the prioritized teams to benefit as well as those applying the intervention. Determine other teams and approaches in the area for addressing this problem/ objective. Examine the degree of problem or goal. Identify the neighborhood problem/goal to be attended to as well as what requires to be done.

2. Applying for Funding through European Funding Agencies

(<https://europa.eu/>) Local business: Can get EU funding with gives, loans as well as warranties. Grants provide direct support, while other funding is readily available via programs handled across the country.

Non-governmental & civil culture organizations:

Might be eligible for financing, given they are active in EU policy areas as well as on a charitable basis.

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Young people: Two main types of financing:

Education and learning & training - research study chances via specif funding firms, support for students nearing the end of additional education and learning, as well as vocational training in an additional nation

Youth- co-funding of tasks which encourage public involvement, volunteer work, and also a more comprehensive multicultural overview.

Researchers:

In between 2014 as well as 2020, the EU will certainly provide practically EUR80bn in financing for study, generally via its front runner research program Perspective 2020. This funding usually takes the form of gives, to part-finance a wide range of research projects.

3. Literature Review

Levine, J., & Writing, G. (2006) This Overview for Composing a Funding Proposal was developed to help encourage individuals to be successful in getting funds for jobs that give worthwhile social solutions. A significant motif that runs throughout the Overview is a concern for the growth of significant cooperative connections -with funding companies, with community organizations, and also with the people you are offering -as a basis for the growth of solid fundable efforts. The Guide is built on the presumption that it is with cooperation and engagement whatsoever levels that long term modification can be affected. Each of the headings utilized in this Overview is recommended as purposeful methods to arrange your very own financing proposal and were identified through an examination of a variety of various proposals creating layouts. The comments and ideas that follow each heading are presented to assist you to prepare a strong and also fundable proposal. The complete overview is available on the global internet as well as consists of not only the ideas and recommendations in this paper, but additionally includes instances of real funding propositions, recommended published products, and also web links to various other proposition creating web sites.

Penrod, J. (2003) As a program of research is created, the small-project gives is an ideal means for launching distinct tasks to construct assistance for bigger funding. The writer describes the growth of an effective small qualitative task proposition on the disabling results of osteoporosis. She studies the process of composing a small-project proposition to help amateur or junior scientists in securing financing for tiny tasks that, she hopes, will certainly build toward funding on a larger scale. Significant parts of the proposition are consisted of in this write-up to show the secrets to success in obtaining tiny qualitative projects funded.

Singh, M. D., Cameron, C., & Duff, D. (2005) In this paper, we give general standards for writing propositions for study funds. These standards put on quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods research proposals. A proposal for study financing provides an overview of the planned research and also is needed by funding companies. The proposal is sent for analysis as well as position by an evaluation committee according to the criteria put forth by that certain agency. It may be required to send propositions to more than one agency to obtain adequate operating as well as framework financing for a research study project.

4. Steps to Follow for Project Proposals**1. Project Title:**

Penrod, J. (2003) Choose a title that reflects the meaning and purpose of the project

2. Applicant:

- ✓ Organization : Name, Address, Telephone number, Mobil Number, Fax Number, Website, Corporate or Company E-Mail ID's and Skype ID (if applicable)
- ✓ Aims of Organization
- ✓ Experience and fields covered
- ✓ Person in charge of the project: Nationality and experience. Should he/she be European, Please state from which province.
- ✓ Indicate how you were referred to specific funding agency.
- ✓ Please state the reference number(s) of any projects presented to Specific Funding agency.

3. Project Location

- ✓ Carey, M. A., & Swanson, J. (2003). State the exact location of the project and include directions of how to get there.
- ✓ Specify the distance in KMS to the nearest city and time taken to cover that distance
- ✓ Describe the geographical characteristics of the area
- ✓ Which are the best months to travel to this area?

4. Project Origins

- ✓ Dean, B. V., & Sengupta, S. S. (1962) How did the idea for the project originate?
- ✓ Explain if the project forms part of a wider existing regional or national programmer.
- ✓ Explain any primary studies or activities undertaken in identifying the need for implementing the project

5. Project Justification

- ✓ Bunker, G., & Thomson, D. (2006) Detailed description of the social, economic, cultural and political conditions of the area
- ✓ Specify the problems and /or needs which the project intends to solve and which make it necessary.

6. Detailed description of the project

- ✓ Haapanen, P., McAnsh, S., Braidwood, E., & Hollingsworth, R. (2013). *Project's Aims*: What is the general purpose of the project? What are its objectives?
- ✓ Project's Goals: What specific goals do you hope to achieve ? (Please number if applicable)
- ✓ *Activities you intend to undertake or measures you will take in order to a achieve your goals.* (Please Indicate clearly what, how, and where for each of these activities and all measures).
- ✓ *Material and Human Resources*: Number of persons required, experience and salaries, Materials required.

7. Schedule for completion:

- ✓ Jacob, D. S. (2003) Estimate the time required for each activity.
- ✓ State the total time required for implementation and completion of the project.

8. Beneficiaries:

- ✓ Project participants. (2019) Total number of direct beneficiaries
- ✓ Total number of indirect beneficiaries
- ✓ Criteria employed in the selection of beneficiaries
- ✓ Male-Female ratio (State percentage %)
- ✓ State how the target population has been involved in the preparation and decision making process of the project and to what extent they will participate in its future development and continuity.
- ✓ Description of their socio-economic and cultural characteristics
- ✓ Ethnic group (if applicable).

9. Viability

Markusson, N., Kern, F., & Watson, J. (2011) (This is a fundamental aspect if the project's execution and continuity is to be guaranteed)

Case explains how the project will work once external financial aid is over.

- ✓ Identify the person(s) responsible for the project and the name of its legal holder (if different).
- ✓ *Socio-Cultural Viability*: cultural aspects that will guarantee the project's success, particularly if it will mean changes in certain life habits.
- ✓ *Economic Viability*: explain how you intend to cover future expenses and how the profits will be distributed among the beneficiaries. (Please be very specific if the project is of a productive nature). Please include a chart showing incomes and expenses.
- ✓ *Technical Viability*: state what technical guarantees you can give with regard to maintenance and management of the project in the future.

10. Following and evaluation of the project

State, resources, follows up and evaluation instruments required.

11. Budget and financial Breakdown:

- ✓ Rahman, M. (2011) A breakdown of the total cost by items must be entered into the table below.
- ✓ The follow must be presented in both local and foreign currency (USD, Euro, etc..) indicating the current rate of exchange
- ✓ Indicate local contributions (land, salaries, etc.), stating clearly whether it is money or in kind.(In the case of the latter, please specify).
- ✓ State any government aid or subsidies from other sources(if any).
- ✓ Indicate whether you intend to apply or have already applied to other organizations for cooperation. In the case that your application has been successful, indicate the amount approved , the financial terms and conditions and the name of the organization.

<i>Items</i>	<i>Local Contribution</i>	<i>Funding Agency</i>	<i>OTHER (Government, Local Councils, International Cooperation, etc.)</i>	<i>TOTAL</i>
1. Initial budgeting costs				
2. Land				
3. Construction				
4. Equipment and materials				
5. Labour/Salaries				
7. Revolving fund				
8. Training				
9.Operational costs				
10. Unforeseen expenses				
11. Administration expenses				
TOTAL :				

Table: 1 Please specify the components for each item

12. Necessary Documents:**General:**

- ✓ Pennock, J. O. (2001) Copy of organization Bylaws and latest Annual report (If applicable)
- ✓ Funding agency might require any letters of recommendation endorsing both the need for the project and the reliability of the organization or individual requesting cooperation.
- ✓ Pro-forma invoices for any items to be purchased , provided by reliable suppliers
- ✓ Letter from the beneficiaries requesting our cooperation and committing themselves to ensuring the continuity of the project in the future
- ✓ Map clearly indicating the location of the project, photos, if possible.
- ✓ Any other relevant documents

Specific:

For Example If Construction projects: Please ensure to include: the architect's plan together with the breakdown of expenses and a technical description signed and stamped by a qualified technician. Deed and document of property for the land.

Productive projects: Please include a market survey

Revolving fund: If you intend to employ a revolving fund, please describe how it will work

5. Conclusion

The majority of funding companies have clear guidelines, instructions, and also overviews of the financing treatments they concentrate on a specific number, for a detailed purpose, issue, and location. Lots of companies make an application for funding to ensure their proposal and structure are according to the decided parameter of funding agencies and they adhere to the method suitably. After the Adjustment Fund Board determines to approve an entity considering the recommendation by the Certification Panel, the entity can send a principle or a complete job proposal. Events looking for financial resources from the Adaptation Fund need to submit their project as well as program propositions through accredited National, Regional, or Multilateral Executing Entities. Proposals will be evaluated relative to specific criteria offered in the Functional Policies and Guidelines. Proposals are accepted three times a year: two times prior to the biannual Adaptation Fund Board conferences and also when throughout an intercessional evaluation cycle.

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